

Database Normalization

By Savindu Mahasen Ruhunehewa

Abstraction

IT (Information technology) is vast area. In present world, lot of students are following this area domain like computer science, software engineering, data science, etc. In most of the domain, students need to learn about the database management system (DBMS). Under the DBMS, normalization is playing vital role and mandatory concept which BSc, MSc and even academics need to know. But, in recently this I have noticed, this normalization concept was difficult for especially BSc, and MSc students and some academics. From this resource, I am going to explain from 1NF (First Normal Form) to BCNF (Boyce Codd Normal Form) normalization concepts.

1. Introduction

When it comes to database normalization, BSc, MSc students face difficulty understanding this concept. As a result, I thought, conducting deep discussions really helped all the BSc, MSc students and other academics. So, then from this resource, I am going to explain normalization forms 1NF (First Normal Form), 2NF (Second Normal Form), 3NF (Third Normal Form) and Boyce Codd Normal Form (BCNF). Before moving to this normalization form, let us understand what normalization is and what is the purpose of using it.

Normalization is a process which is basically analyzing the schema (tables) using primary keys and functional dependencies. To understand this, we need to get to know about primary keys and functional dependencies which mean.

1.1 What is primary key and functional dependency?

Simple definition for primary key is a unique identifier by using that we can identify each record uniquely in a relation. This primary key was selected by database designer identifying tuples in a relation [1]. For an Example let's we consider organization scenario. In the organization scenario, Employee is an entity, EmpNo, Name, Age, Sex are the attributes. In this case normally multiple employees cannot have same EmpNo. EmpNo is like NIC (National Identity Card). Which means every person has unique NIC. Likewise EmpNo also unique. Using specific EmpNO we can identify Name, Age, Sex of that employee.

Functional dependencies (FDs) play significant role in 2NF (Second Normal Form), 3NF (Third Normal Form), and BCNF (Boyce Codd Normal Form). Basically, FDs provide relationships that exist when one attribute uniquely determines another attribute [2]. Which means functional dependency provides constraint (restriction) between two sets of attributes from the database. Functional dependency can be represented as \rightarrow notation.

Emp No \rightarrow Name (Name is dependent on EmpNo, Using EmpNo user can determine employee name. So then, left hand side of above dependency known as determinant).

1.2 What is main purpose of normalization?

The main purpose of this concept is to create tables with minimal redundancy and minimal anomalies. This means that if the same data exists in multiple places in a database and one value

is updated, all related occurrences must also be updated. Otherwise, it leads to data inconsistency, which is called an anomaly. Examples of anomalies are insert, delete, and update

At this point, let's move to Normalization forms by considering primary keys and functional dependencies to form minimal redundancies and anomalies. Normalization can be done in several ways. From this resource, I am planning to explain several ways which user can understand and approach normalization.

1NF (First Normal Form)

1NF (First Normal Form), principles are attributes should be single, atomic (cannot divide further) and relation cannot have duplicate columns [3]. Which means attribute should take a single value instead of multiple values. And composite attributes are not directly allowed. Example like Address. Address is composite attribute which means it is comprised of number, city, and road. Because divisible parts cannot be put into the one cell. We must decompose ourselves to atomic values. The reason is a relation in First Normal Form (1NF) particular cell can contain one value instead of multiple values. Let me explain this more clearly using tables. To explain this, I considered Department of IT company.

Department

<u>DeptNo</u>	DName	DLocation
10001	Computer Engineering	Peradeniya, katugasthota
10002	Research	Peradeniya, Kegalle
1003	IT	Peradeniya, Galaha

Table 1 – Department Table

Let's identify basic elements of above table, first we need to identify primary key, Primary key of relation is DeptNo. According to the above-mentioned principles of 1NF, Department is not first normal form. Because DLocation of above relation is multi value attribute. So, then we have to convert into first normal form. When we are converting into first normal form there are three options available

Option1

Splitting the problematic attribute into a new relation. Let's try to understand more clearly. In the department table, problematic attribute is DLocation, so we need to remove that attribute from default relation and include in the newly created relation.

Department

<u>DeptNo</u>	DName
1001	Computer Engineering
1002	Research
1003	IT

Table 2 – Department

Department Location

<u>DeptNo</u>	<u>DLocation</u>
1001	Peradeniya
1001	Katugasthota
1002	Peradeniya
1002	Kegalle
1003	Peradeniya
1003	Galaha

Table 3 - Department Location

Once we split into two relations, newly created relation still, we redundancy. DeptNo, and DLocation are not unique. So, then we must create composite key by combining DeptNo, and DLocation.

Option 2

When it comes to the option 2 completely different from option 1, the reason is instead of creating a new relation, in the same relation, store the one value in a problematic attribute. As a result, additional rows are created and lot of redundancies have occurred compared to option 1.

After performing 1NF (First Normal Form) using this option 2 table displayed below.

<u>DeptNo</u>	DName	<u>DLocation</u>
1001	Computer Engineering	Peradeniya
1001	Computer Engineering	Katugasthota
1002	Research	Peradeniya
1002	Research	Kegalle
1003	IT	Peradeniya
1003	IT	Galaha

Table 4 – Department

In the table 4, also 1NF table. Because multi value, non-atomic, and duplicate columns are available. Primary key composite key to identify each record uniquely.

Option 3

If a maximum number of values are known in problematic attributes in a relation, in the third option, create the additional attributes to store maximum number of values. In according to the above example, each location attribute holds one location only.

Department

<u>DeptNo</u>	DName	DLocation1	DLocation2
1001	Computer Engineering	Peradeniya	Katugasthota
1002	Research	Peradeniya	Kegalle
1003	IT	Peradeniya	Galaha
1004	HR	Peradeniya	

Table 5 – Department

In this case, redundancies are less compared to the option1, option2. But null values can occur. Let me explain in more detail way. In this case computer engineering, Research, IT, and the HR department has both locations, but when it comes to HR, it has only one location. (Peradeniya). In this case Some departments are located at all locations, and some are at limited location. According to this, there are lot of null values that can occur compared to option 1 and option 2.

Now let's look at how we need to deal when tables have composite attributes (non-atomic values). To explain this, I considered the table and full name, address are composite attributes, and EmpNo as primary key.

Employee

<u>EmpNo</u>	FullName	Address
1001	Savindu, Mahasen, Ruhunuhewa	46, Dehideniya, Muruthalawa
1002	Sewwanththa kumara Premasiri	72, Narampanawa, Kandy
1003	Nayanjith dharmakeerthi Bandara	26, Ambewala, Nuwaraeliya

Table 06 - Employee

So, according to the 1NF (First Normal Form) definition, atomic values can have instead of composite attributes. Above table 06, FullName and Address are composite attributes as I earlier mentioned. Which means Full Name comprised of first name, middle name, last name. Address comprised No, street, city. These divisible parts cannot be put into one cell of relation.

Employee

<u>EmpNo</u>	FirstName	MiddleName	LastName	No	Street	City
1001	Savindu	Mahasen	Ruhunuhewa	46	Dehideniya	Muruthalawa
1002	Sewwanththa	Kumara	Premasiri	72	Narampanawa	Kandy
1003	Nayanajith	Dharmakeerthi	Bandara	26	Ambewala	Nuwaraeliya

Table 07 - Employee

Now, above table comprises simple attributes, not atomic attributes, and non-duplication columns.

To convert the above table 06 into 1NF form there is another way. Which means we can use vertical splitting method.

According to the above table 06, EmpNo is primary key, we can separate that into two tables like below.

Employee

<u>EmpNo</u>	Name
1001	Savindu, Mahasen, Ruhunuhewa
1002	Sewwanththa, kumara, Premasiri
1003	Nayanjith, dharmakeerthi, Bandara

Table 08 - Employee

Employee Location

<u>EmpNo</u>	Address
1001	46, Dehideniya, Muruthalawa
1002	72, Narampanawa, Kandy
1003	26, Ambewala, Nuwaraeliya

Table 09 – Employee Location

Once we splitted the above main table (Table 06) using vertical splitting method, we got two tables, but still not first normalize form, so then, we have to convert the composite attributes into atomic attributes.

<u>EmpNo</u>	First Name	Middle Name	Last Name
1001	Savindu	Mahasen	Ruhunuhewa
1002	Sewwanththa	Kumara	Premasiri
1003	Nayanajith	Dharmakeerthi	Bandara

Table 10 – Employee

<u>EmpNo</u>	No	Street	City
1001	46	Dehideniya	Muruthalawa
1002	72	Narampanawa	Kandy
1003	26	Ambewala	Nuwaraeliya

Table 11 - Employee Location

Above Table 10, 11 are the tables after first normalization. But here is, once we are splitting the Employee table, employee information is divided into two tables, both tables contain employee information. Instead of this splitting method, we can use a method which we use to convert table 06 to table 07.

2NF (Second Normal Form)

Lets' look at Why we need 2NF. The main reason behind this is, most of the time after completing the 1NF, data redundancies will not zero. So then, we need to go with other normal forms as well. In introduction part, already mentioned, normalization is based on primary key and functional dependencies. When it comes to the 1NF, we didn't use functional dependency concept. To explain the 2NF, functional dependency needs to be considered. Because 2NF depends on functional dependency.

Let's consider R (Relation). An X attribute of R is prime if it appears in a candidate key (according to F) of R. And there is Y attribute it is not a prime attribute (Not a part of candidate key). In the 2NF mainly check whether non-prime attributes are fully dependent on prime attributes or not. In relations, sometimes partial dependencies have. If there are partial dependencies, that table doesn't in 2NF. To convert into 2NF, we have to remove from main table and include them in a new relation. Let's consider the real-world example.

In the software engineering organization, typically employees work on projects. Let's consider these Employee and Project entities and their relationship. When it comes to this relationship, we have to think about cardinality ratio. One Employee can work on multiple projects; one project is assigned for multiple employees, And Hours are defined when Employee start working on a particular project. That can represent as (M to N). To clearly explain this scenario, I represented the ER (Entity Relationship) diagram.

Figure 01 - ER diagram

So, when it comes to the M to N, once we convert into relational model schema, intermediate table is created. According to the above ER diagram, our intermediate table is Employee Project. It can be represented like below in relational schema.

So, then we need to identify full dependencies and partial dependencies. In above relational schema, arrows represent the full and partial dependencies. Hours are dependent on all the candidate keys. But, EName depends on SSN, PLocation depends on PNumber. They are called partial dependencies. So then, In the 2NF,

Now we have got three separate tables, with full functional dependencies. And also, 2NF is only relevant when a table has a composite primary key.

3 NF (Third Normal Form)

To convert the relation into 3NF, relation should be already in 2NF. Which means relation cannot contain partial dependencies. Once we converted into 2NF, we need to consider the 3NF. First requirement of 3NF is, table should already be in 2NF and no non-prime attribute of relation (R) is transitively dependent on the primary key.

SSN is the primary key of the relation. It functionally determines eName, bDate, address, and dNumber. However, dName is not directly dependent on SSN. Instead, dName depends on dNumber, and dNumber depends on SSN. Since dNumber is not a candidate key, this creates a **transitive dependency**:

$SSN \rightarrow dNumber \rightarrow dName$.

Above table has transitive dependency, once converted into 3NF. Tables should be like below.

dNumber	dName
---------	-------

Two tables have been created after performing 3NF.

BCNF (Boyce-Codd Normal Form)

BCNF (Boyce-Codd Normal Form), also known as 3.5NF, is stronger than 3NF. The main concept of BCNF is that for every functional dependency $X \rightarrow Y$ in a relation R, X must be a super key. In other words, every determinant must be a key candidate. If this condition is violated, the relation is not in BCNF.

For example,

According to the above relation, zip code is not a super key. In above case zip code \rightarrow City. so then above relation is not in BCNF (3.5NF). Once we convert into BCNF form below are the tables user got.

City	<u>ZipCode</u>
------	----------------

<u>Street</u>	Zipcode
---------------	---------

REFERENCES

- [1] M. R. C. o. E. & Technology, Database Management System, Maisammaguda.
- [2] A. Noor, "Functional Dependency," p. 6, 2021.
- [3] M. Fuchs, "Normalization of Databases," 16 May 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://michael-fuchs-sql.netlify.app/2021/05/16/normalization-of-databases/>. [Accessed 14 April 2026].